

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

SYMBOLIC IMPLICATIONS IN THE IMAGERY OF HEMINGWAY'S PROSE

Orujova I.

Azerbaijan University of Languages,
Azerbaijan,

134, Rashid Behbudov str., Baku, 1014

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10785247>

Abstract

Apart from cognitive function any literary text bears certain aesthetic features which necessarily include the use of tropes, foregrounded syntactic structures and symbolic implications that greatly contribute to the creation of imagery of the prose or poetic writing. The idiosyncratic style of great American modernist writer Ernest Hemingway is famous for numerous artistic techniques ranging from phonetic, lexical and syntactic devices to symbolism, distant realization of meaning and stream of consciousness narrative type. The symbols the writer resorts to are of a multifarious kind; the idiosyncratic imagery of his novels and short stories is frequently based on the use of depiction of animals, inanimate objects, colors, natural phenomena, and even the characters, their thoughts, words and actions. Such symbols stand for expressing human's feelings, emotions and mentality. A unique atmosphere of E. Hemingway's prose contributed by these symbols imparts on the reader the feelings of sadness, desolation, and moral emptiness inherent in the so-called "Lost Generation" of young men who experienced the hardships of the war and to whom the writer belonged to.

Keywords: symbolism, imagery, tropes, idiolect, writing style

Introduction

The basic function of any literary text, be it a prosaic or poetic text, is its cognitive-aesthetic impact on the reader. Works of fiction represent the surrounding reality through the specific use of language that prompts the reader to feel the atmosphere and the spirit of an alternative fictional world recreated in his/her imagination. To impart greater expressiveness to the authors' artistic style, writers resort to various linguistic means of creating peculiar imagery in their creative work. To create an image in fiction literature means to represent general details through the individual perception, the abstract notions through the concrete, sensory-visual, tangible notions [3, p. 12].

The imagery of novels, plays and poems can be created not only by the peculiar use of words and phrases, rather, the idiosyncrasy of author's imaginary world is manifested through such foregrounding elements as symbolism, implicatures, subtext, distant realization of meaning and various figures of speech, including lexical, syntactic and phonetic ones. One of the most significant devices of style-forming aspect is intertwining of symbols into the literary work of literature.

Methodology

Some scientific research conducted in different countries by various scholars in the field of Linguistics and its branch - Stylistics highlighted a number of issues connected with the analysis of writers' idiolect. These problems may include an idiosyncratic use of stylistic tropes, schemes and special syntactic structures mentioned in the article above. The linguo-stylistic analysis held in this paper elicited some cases of symbolic implications E. Hemingway used in his prose works. Further, the analysis of the meanings the symbols stand for was presented with the explanation of stylistic devices and other foregrounded elements the

writer resorts to depicting his symbols for creation of the unique imagery.

Main part

Symbols are allegorical elements, since they contain implications, hints to some facts; they allude without stating openly, therefore, often the meaning of symbols is not easy to identify, recognize and record in the target text according to linguistic norms of the target language. This fact led some scholars to consider symbols to be idiolectal, having value only within the limits of the author's work. Therefore, linguistic symbols take shape only within the context of a writer who uses symbols metonymically to create an emotional atmosphere influencing the reader.

As it is generally recognized, the process of simultaneous perception of realistic imprint and reflection of the surrounding world and the symbolic images of the literary work of fiction occurs during interpersonal communication which is characterized by a pragmatic approach to the interpretation of these symbols. The perception of symbols is often related to the reader's personal vision of certain phenomena, as well as his worldview, cultural norms, education and background knowledge. An artistic detail is viewed as a symbol provided that it is subject to the randomness of the connection between it and the symbolized concept and the repetition of the word it expresses within the given text, which consolidates the once named and explained relationships [2, p. 17].

To understand the mechanism of combining realistic and symbolic images, one should interpret interpersonal discourse, considering a pragmatic approach to their interpretation. This means that most symbols are culturally specific; therefore they are only understood by members of a particular linguistic and cultural community. Symbolic meaning is usually revealed on

the literary level, the realization of symbolic implications is the result of reader's interaction with the text; therefore symbolism prompts the reader to decipher the possible meaning and the motivation for its allegorical decoding. The perception of a symbol also largely depends on the reader's personal understanding of the phenomenon being described, his/her worldview, cultural and linguistic norms of society.

The unique style of Ernest Hemingway has been studied by linguists and literary scholars; yet, some linguistic features he preferred in his works have been unduly underestimated. To them we can justly refer such linguistic means as symbolism and implicatures, distant realization of meaning and various tropes, figures of speech and stylistic devices, including lexical, syntactic and even phonetic ones. Nevertheless, E. Hemingway treats the image as a functional category, correlating objective reality with the imaginative world. Striving for a realistic reflection of reality, E. Hemingway invented a symbolic language in which surrounding world is depicted through symbolic images. E. Hemingway's use of symbols is based more on logical inferences than on open explanations. The writer resorts to the symbolism of associations in order to convey the main meaning through hints and hidden implications. The method of symbolic reflection of reality used by him is the transfer of subjective conditions surrounding his characters and influencing their behavior. The linguistic means used by the author do not directly create an emotional background; rather, they simply predetermine it.

The technique of intertwining symbolic images used by E. Hemingway does not violate the natural, realistic course of events or the narrative of the plot; rather, it synthesizes the reality with the fictional world. The writer resorts to symbolism with extreme caution strictly adhering to realism in artistic depiction and basing the images on their similarity. E. Hemingway's harmoniously depicted symbolic images are the inevitable components that characterize the short, economical style of E. Hemingway's literary works. Thus, in his prose the reader encounters symbolic images realized through the symbolic subtext emphasized by repeated phrases that act as implications, such as the following distantly located metaphorical phrases "pools of water", "wet dead leaves", and so on. These images evoke certain associations in the readers' imagination - dead bodies of people, pools of blood. Symbols of death and suffering permeate most of E. Hemingway's stories and novels creating a specific subtext. The interpretation of such symbols is possible owing to the stylistic repetition of phrases, which adds semantic significance to symbolic objects:

They shot the six cabinet ministers at half-past six in the morning against the wall of the hospital. There were pools of water in the courtyard. There were wet dead leaves on the paving of the courtyard. It rained hard. All the shutters of the hospital were nailed shut. One of the ministers was sick with typhoid. Two soldiers carried him downstairs and out into the rain. They tried to hold him up against the wall but he sat down in a puddle of water. The other five stood very quietly against the wall. Finally the officer told the soldiers it

was no good trying to make him stand up. When they fired the first volley he was sitting down in the water with his head on his knees [1, p. 95].

As it is clear from the passage the order of cause-and-effect is apparently violated, as "pools of water" should serve as the effect of the phrase "It rained hard", therefore the phrase "wet dead leaves" stand to symbolize dead bodies soaked in blood. Moreover, the courtyard stands for a bloodshed killing ground, but the hospital with the nailed shutters evokes a grave or a tomb in the reader's mind. As the writer went through two wars the use of the abovementioned symbols becomes natural and they contribute to the gloomy description of the executions, intensifying the artistic effect. E. Hemingway uses the images of water and rain in the situations where death is inevitable, though as a trite symbol water usually signifies purification and renewal of life compared to dryness and drought, dangerous and sometimes even fatal for humans.

E. Hemingway introduced the style of writing which was innovatory for his time – the form of psychological sketch which greatly favors for such techniques as prevalence of dialogues over monologues, detailed description of physical actions, understatement and vagueness of the events happening around, the abundant use of repetitions and key words [4, p.16]. As it is obvious from the passage, the writer resorts to the stylistic device of repetition which greatly contributes to the effect of creating the image of the characters and their feelings, emotions and behavior. In the passage the repetition of the numeral "six" imparts certain rhythm on the utterance strengthening the emotional influence on the reader. The repetitions E. Hemingway uses are of multifarious nature, some of them are simple lexical repetitions, not fixed in any concrete place of the sentences. Most of the other repetitions are anaphora, epiphora or chain repetition. The variety of writer's repetitions includes the repetition of the key words, similar parallel constructions or words belonging to the same part of speech, clauses with the anaphoric use of the same conjunctions, etc. [4, p. 17].

In some of E. Hemingway's stories and novels the symbolic image of home stands for well-being, security, friendship and other positive associations. Conversely, the image of bulls frequently encountered in writer's prose symbolizes power and weakness simultaneously as the bulls and sometimes even matadors at the end of the bullfights die:

...Then he cursed the bull, flopped the muleta at him, and swung back from the charge his feet firm, the muleta curving and at each swing the crowd roaring... When he started to kill it was all in the same rush... [1, p. 141].

E. Hemingway artfully includes images of animals and objects which symbolize multifarious abstract notions, the symbol of death being one of the widely spread in his prose. Such images as vultures, hyenas, and the dead leopard clearly stand for death, as the main characters eventually die in the stories and novels. The reader in any country belonging to different culture can easily decipher the meaning of these symbols from the context:

“... *I'm dying now. Ask those bastards*”. *He looked over to where the huge, filthy birds sat, their naked heads sunk in the hunched feathers. A fourth planed down, to run quick-legged and then waddle slowly towards the others. [1, p. 40].*

The image of the animals is a much favored device the writer used to allude to death, just like the image of hyena which can be found in many of his stories. The sinister mood is achieved in connection with the atmosphere of the surrounding nature and the premonition the character feels hearing hyena whimpering and afterwards when he dies at night:

Just then the hyena stopped whimpering in the night and started to make a strange, human, almost crying sound... [1, p. 56].

An extremely remarkable case of the symbol tuning the reader to the mood of the whole story can be found in E. Hemingway's story “The Snows of Kilimanjaro” where the epigraph contains the image of the carcass of the dead leopard, along with a number of other symbols, such as vultures, hyenas, guns and other images which symbolize death:

...Close to the western summit there is the dried and frozen carcass of a leopard. No one has explained what the leopard was seeking at that altitude [1, p. 39].

Such a symbolic precursor of the forthcoming tragic events is realized through the contrastive images described at the beginning of the story in its epigraph; the figure of a dead animal stands on the background of the magnificently looking Mount Kilimanjaro, “the Masai House of God”. The juxtaposition of the two objects contains the allusive symbolic reference. The image of the dead leopard serves a symbol of the main character's death on the peak of his life and career. The leopard like the main character dies in the alien country, far from his home, in search of new thrills, new emotions and unexplored things.

The idiosyncratic nature of Hemingway's writing style can also be traced in symbolic reflection of some images of characters of his prose works. Such a technique reveals the writer's inner feelings and attitudes and serves to develop a plot of the story or novel. The correlative mythological symbols implicitly express the psychological conflicts of E. Hemingway's characters. Linguistically, the symbolic embodiment is transferred by means of metaphor, metonymy, similes, epithets and other tropes:

Because, just then, death had come and rested its head on the foot of the cot and he could smell its breath [1, p. 54].

“Never believe any of that about a scythe and a skull,” he told her. “It can be two bicycle policemen as easily, or be a bird. Or it can have a wide snout like a hyena” [1, p. 54].

As follows from the samples above, all E. Hemingway's prose works are full of symbolic implications, most of which are built on contrast, antithesis, a peculiar kind of symbols present contrasting images of death and well-being or valor and suffering. Thus, in the short story named “Soldier's Home” E. Hemingway juxtaposes the sense of friendship, affection and strife for better life to the gloomy routine of where boredom, low-paid job and pessimistic mood of prejudiced town

reigned. Such sinister symbols are conveyed by eloquent metaphors or metonymic utterances. To create symbols, besides stylistic foregrounding the writer frequently turns to the distant realization of lexical meaning in which symbols can be felt only if the reader attentively reads the longer passage. The distant realization of symbolic meaning in combination with juxtaposition, or antithesis is one of E. Hemingway's most favored literary device of symbols creating. The great variety of writer's techniques can also include inanimate objects, such as, for example, the axe and the gun in Hemingway's short story, symbolizing masculinity, virility and power. Conversely, the Bible in the woman character's hands emphasizes vulnerability and hints at the forthcoming conflict between the characters.

The symbolic representation of E. Hemingway's prose can be created via metaphoric, metonymic transference, in some cases by similes or antonomasia (personification). Even the colors of the characters' faces can symbolize passion, courage and vitality of the red face and on the opposite, weakness and cowardice of the white face. Such opposition is apparent in the short story “The Short Happy Life of Francis Macomber” where the brave hunter's face, “red faced swine”, is opposed to white hunter's face of a coward. Hemingway associates the brave red-faced hunter with the fearless animal—the lion. The strong animal lion is the totemistic symbol for the two hunters representing their ego after the death of the animal. The antagonistic position of human versus animal is deeply rooted in human's mythological past and can often be met in Hemingway's stories and novels. The juxtaposition of man and the animals is reflected even in the Christian religion where the lion symbolizes solidarity, love and humility as opposed to isolated man's individualism and pride.

In his creative works E. Hemingway artfully shows the contradiction in man and nature by using a great variety of techniques of symbolic creations. For this reason he uses the images of mountains, hills, plains, rivers, and even mud. If the image of an animal bears not only its original metaphorical allusion to man's limitations and it can also symbolize man's vulnerability in his power and evolution, the landscape settings serve to create the atmosphere of moral crisis and emotional emptiness, that is realized through the image of dry barren land, lifeless hills, mud, dry rivers, etc. Analyzing Hemingway's symbolic images it is easy to prove the fact that he frequently creates conventional symbols and greatly unexpected idiolectal symbols. The language means he turns to include epithets combined with metaphors and metonymy, opposing lexical units of positive connotations with the words of negative connotation interwoven into the unique antithesis and oxymoron.

Findings

Thus, the realistic narration in Hemingway's prose works is achieved due to the controversial nature of various images introduced by means of skillful combination of a range of language means, tropes, stylistic devices and symbolism being the leading ones. The unique imagery created by the writer is greatly contrib-

uted by the images of protagonists, their feelings, beliefs and actions, frequently depicted by symbols which stand for characters, as well as by phenomena of nature and the material images. Besides those symbols sometimes E. Hemingway uses the technique of so-called "distant realization of meaning" when the symbolic implication is realized within the longer passage of the text and they could be scattered throughout the whole work. The symbolic meaning of Hemingway's prose is attached to images of various types forming the general system of imagery of the whole literary work. The system of imagery and the symbolic inclusion foster the dynamics of the plot development. The unusual tech-

nique of creating imagery with the inclusion of symbolic implications is the distinctive feature of Hemingway's writing style.

References:

1. Hemingway, Ernest. The Complete Short Stories of Ernest Hemingway. New-York – London: Finca Vigia Edition, 2003
2. Krylova, V.V. Transformation of English An-tonomasia into Russian //Translation and Text Interpretation. M.: Institute of Linguistics, 1988
3. Kukharenko V.A. Idiolectal Literary Style and the Research. Kiev-Odessa: Higher School,1980
4. Orujova, Irina. Ernest Hemingway in Russian Translation. Lambert Academic Publishing, 2017